

Familiarity vs ambiguity: Exploring the potentials of ambiguity in user interface design

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Abstract In this paper the importance of using familiarity vs ambiguity in design and the possible implications of applying ambiguity in product design are explored and discussed. Because of recent technological developments and the increase of interactive products, user interfaces have become more ambiguous for certain users. Smart devices stretch the context in which the products are usually used. With help from research in other fields, the appeal of ambiguity is explored and the relevance for the field of design is explained. Our conclusion is that ambiguity can be beneficial for users especially for providing novel and exciting experiences, yet some users will not be able to tolerate ambiguity. Designers should therefore handle ambiguity with care. Thus, they can aim to design familiar yet ambiguous interfaces to keep the balance between ease of use and highly affective product experience.

Keywords *Ambiguity, Familiarity, Metaphors, User interfaces, Product design*

Introduction

Human Computer Interaction has increased over the last 15 years due to the development of personal devices like smartphones, tablets and computers, significantly changing the way people interact with products (Harvard Business Review, 2014 and Emarketer, 2015). Consequently, the way that the user interfaces (UIs) of these products were designed became increasingly important. As a consequence of these technological developments, a visual language needed to be created for products that users were not familiar with. With the designers' design space foremost dominated by ambiguous shapes that represent computer functions, there was an urgency to present the virtual shapes in a more familiar way to the users. As a result, ambiguity has been avoided in UI designs and instead familiar objects were chosen to signify a function in a digital platform (e.g., see Figure 1 for the image of a trash bin representing the function of deleting digital files (see also Gaver, 1989)). However, this paper discusses the current needs in UI design and its relevance for ambiguity.

Familiar yet Ambiguous?

The tendency to facilitate ease of use by adding familiar elements within the design of UI is not strange. Research on familiarity revealed that repeated exposure to a certain stimulus makes people like this

stimulus better (Bornstein, 1989; Zajonc, 1968, 1980). This process is referred to in literature as mere exposure effect (MEE), which can both occur when individuals are consciously aware of stimuli as well as unconsciously (Bornstein, 1989). Familiar objects also have the capacity to elicit a mental model in users which encompass previous experiences with the object and conceptually and contextually relevant knowledge. Similarly, mental models and knowledge adhering to an object should shape and affect behaviour (Marks & Olson, 1981). That is, as users have been already repeatedly exposed to daily objects and have familiarity with them, seeing known objects on User Interfaces creates a sense of comfort and safety while navigating through the product.

One way to achieve familiarity and subsequently facilitate ease of use is through the use of metaphors. Metaphors are defined in contemporary theories as *a structuring of our cognitive system* (Lakoff, 1987; Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). That means that metaphors have their effect on the way we perceive the world as well as how we categorize experiences and organize our thoughts (Casakin, 2007). Metaphors are valuable for designers in a sense that it could enable them to understand unfamiliar design problems by juxtaposing them with known situations. Metaphors might have a fundamental role as they are said to

Figure 1. The evolution of the recycle bin in Microsoft's Windows operating system through the years.

Figure 2. The Fonckel one, a LED luminaire that brings together multi – touch sensing, and our human bodily and emotional experience. The user can control the light of the luminaire by making gestures on the multi – touch surface on the back. The gestures needed to operate the light make use of metaphors. That means, waking up the light is done by making an upward gesture over back of the luminaire, where after the light will follow your hand. When you want to broaden the light, you simply make a stretching gesture on the back of the luminaire, for a more focussed light you pinch. With this the LED luminaire enables people to shape light almost as if they can grab it directly with their hands, making it their own personalized expression. (Studio Philip Ross, 2015).

guide reasoning and enhance innovative thinking. Subsequently allowing the designer to think unconventionally as well as encouraging the implementation of novel ideas to design problems (Casakin, 2007). Therefore, metaphors are instrumental for designers and users of UIs, enabling designers to make the abstract understandable by means of evoking familiarity. Consequently making the introduction of a complex technology bearable for novel users.

Nowadays the once complex technologies are properly integrated in the daily life of most modern societies. Users have more experience with using UIs found in their tablets, phones, refrigerators, game consoles, home heating control systems. Therefore with metaphors, designers have more liberty to use form that resembles less and less the source object to represent the targeted function or desired message through abstraction techniques (Cila, 2013). In addition to that, interaction with technology starts early in childhood – the present generation of computers users are often referred to as digital natives - making the need for familiarity no longer essential. For children everything is ambiguous at a certain stage in their life because their brain operates continuously at this unstable state - are thus far better equipped to learn to use novel, unclear interactions. This is in contrast with the elderly of today who often resort to what they know about familiar objects, because it is safe. One could argue that the transition period between the non – digital age and the digital age is over for younger generations since digital natives have already adapted to digital systems.

It is particularly interesting to see how UI designs will change over the years with the digital natives as the future users, because UIs are not only limited to the functional digital products anymore. Certain ‘crossover’ accessories have made their entrance into contemporary home environments (smart lamps,

Figure 3. Philips’ HUE system, which allows users to adjust the lighting characteristics of light sources (intensity and colour temperature) through their smartphone. The system allows the user to control all lighting sources in home through the use of an app, meaning that you do not have to switch on each luminaire individually. It even allows users to schedule different lighting settings through the course of a day or let the system change the lighting dynamically. It furthermore allows users to change the characteristics of light source individually, making that the interaction with the product differs from the interaction you have with ordinary light sources. (Philips, 2015).

interactive walls and interactive tables). For example, the Fonckel One designed by Studio Philip Ross (see in Figure 2) and the Philips HUE system (see in Figure 3), from which the interaction is different in comparison to ordinary lighting sources. These emerging product categories will probably be commonplace in future households, seemingly making a meaningful addition to the furniture that people already own, however raising the question if creating full familiarity is still a necessity for these products; or whether there are other ways to make the use of metaphors more intriguing.

One could even argue that some of the metaphors that were meant to evoke familiarity in UIs have lost their connection to the real world, at least for some users. This is best demonstrated by looking at the future generations of product users: the children of today. To some extent everything is ambiguous for children, since they learn about the context of products when they grow up. It is interesting that children growing up in the coming years will come across certain app icons (for instance) from which they know the consequences - they *know* what will happen when they tap the icon - but they will not understand *why* the interaction they have to make with the application is shaped the way it is. For example, the ‘call’ option on your phone still uses the archetypical phone to indicate its purpose and some archetypical characteristics. Most children growing up right

now have probably never seen an old fashioned phone (at home) that is similar to this archetypical phone, so it is not possible for them to make the connection between the interaction and the actual purpose of the product. More examples of the same issue could be found, for example the floppy disk – shaped save button in MS Word.

It may seem as if consciously incorporating familiarity through metaphors has lost its purpose over time, however the opposite is true. Using obvious metaphors referring to archaic principles is instrumental in retaining involvement of the elderly users of digital systems. However, in such cases familiarity is often retained through analogical references (i.e., seeing an analogue phone horn indicates 'call' function). When the source for the metaphor and the target function are conceptually very closely related, identification of the function in UI is cognitively rather easy and affectively not so intriguing (Cila, Özcan & Hekkert, 2012). Understanding the interaction needed to use the product without having metaphors (AKA analogies, in this case) that create familiarity, could prove to be rather difficult and even dissatisfactory due to inconsistencies between expectations and reality (Anderson & Jolson, 1973).

This creates a certain dilemma for designers; although there is valid foundation for using analogies and metaphors for creating familiarity, using them might also be redundant or even limiting to the experience products can offer to users. Analogies could be limiting since it has been asserted that familiarity hinders creativity and even critical thinking. Novelty on the other hand and some level of ambiguity can create more exciting interfaces (Hekkert et al, 2003). Designers aim to provide users with rich experiences through the product design (e.g., evoking positive emotions as well as negative emotions through design, Fokkinga, & Desmet, 2012). If metaphors are used cleverly, they can also create rather rich experiences because they create duality in meaning attribution (Hekkert & Cila, 2015). Similarly, across the fields of design, arts and literature ambiguity, as well, is seen as a source for providing users with rich experiences. According to Gaver, Beaver and Benford (2003, p. 1) because an ambiguous object is "*intriguing, mysterious and delightful. It leaves space for people's own interpretation encouraging them to play with concepts and their context, which eventually will establish a more personal relation with the meaning offered by those systems.*" Taking part in the meaning making process could be important since this creates a sense of achievement and satisfaction for users.

Why ambiguity works

It is interesting to explore *why* embedding ambiguity in designs across all disciplines is regarded as a worthwhile choice despite the possibility of excluding certain users (e.g., elderly or culturally different users). In other fields, (e.g., different fields of art and politics), advances are made with exploring the reasons of people to favour ambiguity. It is interesting to see whether insights found in these fields of study are applicable to product design.

A study led by psychologist Claudia Muth in which participants were asked to evaluate paintings, showed that when the perceived degree of ambiguity was higher within an artwork, the higher the appreciation was of the participants for the artwork. Participants explained their higher appreciation with the argumentation that they found the ambiguous artworks more interesting and affecting. However, the

research revealed that 'figuring out' the meaning of an art piece was not linked to this pleasure. The research showed that a work's solvability was in no way connected to the liking of the painting and negatively linked to interest and emotional involvement. Therefore, the researchers claimed that: "*A complete resolution of ambiguity is not necessary for the appreciation of an artwork.*" (Muth, Hesslinger & Carbon, 2015).

Another study exploring the importance of ambiguity in relation to the human brain argued the following: The human brain operates close to an unstable point, as revealed by synergetics (Fuller, 1975) and the theory of complexity (BusinessDictionary, 2015). Argued is that the human brain can only create new forms of behaviour when operating close to criticality. Hence ambiguity in art should be considered as an important tool, because ambiguity is according to the researchers in particular suited to keep the brain near this unstable, critical state (Yevin, 2006).

Based on the insights gained from research to ambiguity in fields other than product design can be argued that there is a valid foundation for using ambiguity. Not for the sole reason of enjoyment of ambiguity, but rather for its apparent indispensable ability to keep the brain within an unstable state, receptive to new stimuli which are essential for continued creation and learning.

Conclusion

By exploring the relevance of ambiguity and familiarity in UI design, it became apparent that there are some merits to both principles. Familiarity is essential for making UIs that can be understood by any user. Metaphors, as well as analogies, play an instrumental role in achieving familiarity since they play a role in the way we perceive the world and frame our experiences. Metaphors furthermore facilitate designers in their desire to solve design problems, because metaphors can enhance innovative thinking and thereby help designers to implement novel ideas to design problems. However, the general opinion from a designer's perspective is that with the help of ambiguity designers can offer users richer product experiences and the interactions that people have with products can stretch beyond the expectations of the users leaving space for intrigue, excitement, and sense of discovery.

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